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Endothelial Dysfunction in the Cardiovascular System and Cardiac Injury

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ABSTRACT

The endothelium, composed of a single layer of endothelial cells, maintains vascular homeostasis by regulating vascular tone, coagulation, inflammation, and permeability. Under physiological conditions, it releases mediators such as nitric oxide (NO) that promote vasodilation and prevent thrombosis. However, exposure to cardiovascular risk factors like oxidative stress, inflammation, hypertension, diabetes, and metabolic disturbances leads to endothelial dysfunction (ED). This state is characterized by reduced NO bioavailability, elevated reactive oxygen species (ROS), and pro-inflammatory signaling, resulting in vascular constriction, platelet aggregation, and endothelial activation. ED plays a pivotal role in the onset and progression of atherosclerosis, hypertension, myocardial infarction, and heart failure. Emerging mechanisms, including endothelial senescence and endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition, further aggravate vascular and cardiac damage. As a reversible and early marker of cardiovascular injury, ED provides opportunities for early diagnosis and therapeutic intervention through lifestyle modification, antioxidants, and pharmacological agents aimed at restoring endothelial integrity and function.

Keywords: *Endothelium, cardiovascular injury, endothelial dysfunction, endothelial, vascular disease*

INTRODUCTION

The vascular endothelium is a monolayer of cells lining inside of blood vessels (arteries, veins, capillaries), lymphatic vessels, heart and cavities. Endothelium is considered the largest endocrine organ in the body and plays a crucial regulatory role in cardiovascular health and overall homeostasis (blood flow in heart, fluid exchange, and immune responses) through a variety of mechanisms. It consists of simple squamous epithelial cells lining blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, and the heart, weighs about 1.5 kg and is now recognized as an intelligent barrier and key controller of blood circulation in both micro- and macro-vascular systems of the heart [1][2].

Endothelial function is vital as it interacts with nearly every bodily system by delivering nutrients and growth factors to organs in a targeted manner, while also receiving active metabolites and recycling them into the bloodstream of heart. Moreover, healthy endothelial cells control vascular permeability by releasing a balance between contracting (like endothelin-1, angiotensin II) and relaxing (like prostacyclin, nitric oxide [NO], and endothelium-derived hyperpolarizing factors) factors. They also maintain vascular tone, hemostasis, and anti-thrombotic surfaces [3, 4]

In normal physiology, mechanical forces (shear stress from laminar flow) and agonists (e.g. acetylcholine, bradykinin) stimulate endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) to produce NO, causing smooth muscle relaxation, inhibition of platelet aggregation, and maintenance of an anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant vascular lining in the heart [5]. Endothelial cells also secrete growth factors and cytokines that support vascular repair and quiescence. In this way the endothelium is an active “organ” that preserves vessel

homeostasis in cardiovascular system under healthy conditions[5, 6].

The dysfunction of the endothelium, manifested by reduced NO bioavailability and a shift to a pro-inflammatory, pro-thrombotic phenotype, has been realized to be one of the major early pathophysiological responses in several cardiovascular diseases[4]. The loss of NO-mediated vasodilation and the acquisition of vasoconstrictor factors lead to unopposed vasoconstriction, platelet adhesion, leukocyte recruitment, smooth muscle proliferation, and thrombosis, whereas the endothelium loses its protective functions when it is damaged or stressed (by risk factors such as hypertension, hyperlipidemia, smoking, diabetes, or mechanical stress)[7, 8].

These changes give the grounds to myocardial end-organ ischemia with infarction, microvascular disease, hypertension, atherosclerotic plaque formation and plaque unsteadiness or may cause trauma of heart muscle, valves or cardiac chambers. As a result, endothelial dysfunction (ED) serves as both a marker and mediator of cardiovascular risk [9][10]. This paper explores the endothelium's physiology, the processes and indicators of its malfunction, and how it contributes to cardiovascular and coronary pathology, including myocardial infarction, atherosclerosis, hypertension, and heart failure.

Molecular processes (NO, oxidative stress, inflammation, shear signaling), diagnostic techniques (flow-mediated dilatation, imaging, biomarkers), recent developments in research, clinical consequences, and existing and new treatments (pharmacological, lifestyle, gene, and cell therapies) are cited.

PHYSIOLOGY OF THE ENDOTHELIUM

Endothelial cells form a continuous single cell lining over the inner surface of all blood vessels. They are functionally heterogeneous, for example, coronary microvascular endothelium differs from that in skeletal muscle or kidney but share key roles.

The endothelium, as a reactive tissue, responds to various external and intrinsic stimuli such as stress, immune reactions, neurohumoral signals, medications, shear stress, and pressure, and under normal conditions it sustains basal perfusion regulated by cardiac output and vascular resistance; however, in disease states like inflammation, aging, infection, or injury, its function becomes impaired, disrupting the balance between vasodilatory and vasoconstrictive factors that regulate local blood flow.

Among these, nitric oxide (NO) is the key signaling or vasodilator molecule, produced by endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) from L-arginine under shear stress, which diffuses into smooth muscle cells to activate guanylate cyclase and induce cGMP-dependent vasodilation.

Since NO forms the cornerstone of endothelial regulation, its biochemical role is crucial, and when NO-mediated vasodilation and platelet inhibition are impaired, compensatory mechanisms involving cytochrome-derived factors, natriuretic peptides, prostacyclin (PGI₂), and endothelial-derived hyperpolarizing factors (EDHFs) act to maintain vascular homeostasis [11, 12].

Endothelial dysfunction pulls off the equilibrium between vasodilation and

vasoconstriction in disease situations, frequently leading to a shift toward constrictive dominance. Cyclooxygenase (COX), primarily COX-1 but also COX-2 when activated, is a key regulator of this balance. It transforms arachidonic acid into endoperoxides, which are then converted into prostacyclin, prostaglandins, and thromboxane A₂ (TXA₂).

When vasodilatory function is compromised, thrombus formation is aided by TXA₂-mediated vasoconstriction and the direct contractile effects of serotonin on smooth muscle cells. In healthy conditions, thrombin stimulates inducible NO release, while platelet-derived serotonin and ADP enhance NO synthesis to promote vasodilation [13]. In addition to a tone, the endothelium is a messenger of hemostasis and inflammation.

In the dormant state it offers an anticoagulant surface (expressing thrombomodulin, heparan sulfate, tissue-type plasminogen activator, etc.) and maintains a circulation of leukocytes that do not stick [5]. The endothelial cells on activation by injury or cytokine increase the expression of adhesion molecules (VCAM -1, ICAM -1, E -selectin, P -selectin) and chemokines which attract leukocytes and monocytes to the vessel wall.

They cause an imbalance towards coagulation and inflammation as well. The endothelium, therefore, actively perceives and communicates mechanical and chemical (shear stress, hormones, neurotransmitters) signals into vascular outcomes that facilitate homeostasis [14].

Fig. 1: Different territories of endothelium are shown (at the top) with physiological functions of Endothelium (at bottom).

In summary, a healthy endothelium maintains homeostatic vascular tone, inhibits thrombosis and inflammation, and supports vascular repair (**Figure.1**). This “endothelial homeostasis” relies on adequate NO and other mediators, an intact glycocalyx, and balanced cell signaling. Disruption of these processes (e.g. oxidative stress or neurohormonal factors) leads to *endothelial dysfunction*, a pathologic state that predisposes to cardiovascular injury and diseases.

Hence, healthy endothelium promotes vascular repair, prevents inflammation and thrombosis, and preserves homeostatic vascular tone. An intact glycocalyx, regulated cell signaling, and sufficient NO and other mediators are necessary for this "endothelial homeostasis."

When these mechanisms are disrupted (for example, by neurohormonal hormones or

oxidative stress), endothelial dysfunction occurs, which is a pathologic state that increases the risk of cardiovascular injury and diseases [4, 5].

MECHANISMS OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is a disorder that impairs the endothelium's normal functions. It is distinguished by a decreased availability of nitric oxide (NO), increased vasoconstriction, oxidative stress, inflammation, and a proclivity for thrombosis as shown in (**Figure. 2**). ED is frequently associated with the loss of the endothelium's anticoagulant and anti-inflammatory characteristics, as well as disruptions in vascular growth regulation and remodeling. A significant characteristic of ED, as revealed in multiple investigations, is the reduction of endothelial-dependent relaxation due to

decreased NO activity within the arterial wall [5, 13, 15].

Fig. 2: Different reasons and mechanisms of endothelial dysfunction.

Endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) is constantly expressed and controlled under normal physiological environments by a number of agonists and shear stress. However, eNOS expression or activity is decreased or the enzyme becomes "uncoupled" in endothelial dysfunction, resulting in the production of superoxide rather than nitric oxide (NO). A lack of necessary cofactors like tetrahydrobiopterin or substrates like L-arginine frequently causes this uncoupling. Higher concentrations of asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), a naturally occurring NOS inhibitor, can also lessen the synthesis of NO [14],[16]. Meanwhile, too much reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced by mitochondria, xanthine oxidase, and NADPH oxidase quickly neutralize NO to form peroxynitrite, which reduces its vasodilatory effect and harms the endothelium[8]. Therefore, oxidative stress, which is frequently observed in diseases like diabetes, smoking, and dyslipidemia, not only lowers the availability of NO but also plays a role in endothelial damage. When major cardiovascular risk factors including smoking, obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia eventually converge on these pathways, NO signaling is disrupted and the balance is shifted in favor of vasoconstriction, inflammation,

and thrombosis towards cardiac injury [9]. Also, endothelial dysfunction entails the interruption of the endothelial barrier. The impairment can be local or systemic depending upon the pathology. The loss of barrier functionality in a localized fashion may result in edema and the migration of leukocytes, which are major symptoms of inflammation[17]. Under normal conditions, the endothelium inhibits coagulation, leukocyte-platelet adhesion as it sustains the anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity[18]. Upon endothelial dysfunction, it switches to a pro-inflammatory and pro-coagulant state, with the up-regulation of tissue factor von Willebrand factor (vWF), and down-regulation of tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) those all suppress the fibrinolysis. Systemic dysfunction of endothelium may also lead to extensive vascular permeability, inflammation, thrombocytopenia, and disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), and localized dysfunction to cause venous thrombosis[19, 20]. Arterial endothelial cells, in contrast to venous or microvascular endothelial cells, are encircled by smooth muscle and adventitia. So, endothelial cells experience high shear stress, that leads to copious production of nitric oxide (NO) to keep the vascular walls relaxed. The dysfunction of

these cells in atherogenesis is frequently associated with the 'Response-to-Injury Hypothesis' that indicates the cardiac injury induced by 'platelet adhesion and platelet activation' in response to endothelial injury and 'sub-endothelial matrix exposure' through collagen imbalance [21, 22]. This cardiac injury and endothelial damage may be caused by the toxic stimuli, such as oxidized cholesterol, cigarette smoke, elevated blood lipids, elevated glucose, or irregular blood flow under the influence of hypertension[23]. Activation of platelets subsequently facilitates release of growth factors which stimulate migration, proliferation and formation of fibrous plaques of smooth muscle cells in endothelium and coronary arteries. Although endothelial injury is viewed as the initial phase of atherosclerosis, it is unclear whether it is directly related to lesion formation, since in animal research there is evidence of fatty streaks, but no apparent intimal injury or platelet adhesion. Nevertheless, proteins like high-mobility group protein (HMGB-1), heat shock proteins (HSPs) are known to be released by injured endothelium, and could be involved in cardiac injury process [24, 25].

The other important driver is cardiovascular inflammation. NF- κ B activation in endothelial cells threatened by cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1, IL-2, IL-6) and immune cells can cause increased expression of adhesion molecules (VCAM-1, ICAM-1), tissue factor, and chemokines. Before atherosclerosis occurs chronic vascular inflammation causes endothelial activation, making the surface sticky to leukocytes and platelets [7, 26]. Further, Oxidized lipids (oxLDL) and byproducts of metabolism including advanced glycation end products (in diabetes) and homocysteine may directly harm the endothelium and increase reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation. As an example, oxLDL stimulates the

LOX-1 receptor resulting in oxidative stress and apoptosis of endothelial cells. Mechanical forces are also involved—steady laminar blood flow under normal conditions induces protective genes, eNOS expression facilitated by c-Src/NF κ B signaling, and endothelial barrier integrity under normal conditions [27]]. Moreover, reduced stimulatory (Ser1177) and increased inhibitory (Thr495) phosphorylation disrupts key signaling pathways in endothelial cells caused by endothelial dysfunction (ED). Concomitantly, the pro-oxidant enzyme like NADPH oxidase and mitochondrial ROS increase, and antioxidant defenses like SOD, catalase and glutathione become inadequate [28]. Endothelial mechanotransduction pathways (via caveolae, PECAM-1, integrins) become dysregulated, impairing normal NO release [29, 30]. Under the condition of chronic stress, endothelial cells can either undergo apoptosis or convert by endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EndMT), which facilitates fibrosis and weakly plaques in atherosclerosis [31, 32]. Hence, in nutshell, the pathological changes in endothelial dysfunction alter vascular homeostasis and some of the biomarkers can be quantified for the early detection and monitoring. These biomarkers include reduction of nitric oxide (NO), increase of asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), heightened von Willebrand factor (vWF), and some other inflammatory mediators. Some of these biomarkers have been addressed in the following section.

BIOMARKERS OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION

Since endothelial dysfunction is an internal process, surrogate biomarkers are used to detect it. The brachial artery's flow-mediated dilatation (FMD) and the index of reactive hyperemia (measured by peripheral arterial tonometry) are functional biomarkers that we will discuss under diagnostics. Biomarkers, which can

be found in tissues or blood, are biochemical biomarkers of ED as well. Common indicators include von Willebrand factor (vWF), which is released by damaged endothelium, and circulating asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), an endogenous eNOS inhibitor. Endothelial damage is indicated by a higher concentration of blood circulation endothelial cells or microparticles. Both a high level of inflammatory indicators like high-sensitivity CRP and soluble adhesion molecules (sICAM-1, sVCAM-1, and E-selectin) tend to rise with ED[33]. New biomarkers candidate has appeared e.g. endocan (endothelial cell-specific molecule-1) which is a proteoglycan released by the activated endothelium; plasma endocan concentrations are associated with inflammation and could indicate ED. Other indicators of endothelial activation or dysfunction have also been examined, such as matrix metalloproteinases (MMP-7, MMP-9), angiotensin-like 2 (ANGPTL2), soluble endoglin and annexin V-positive microparticles. Practically, there is no single blood test with a definitive diagnosis of ED, risk information can be obtained in the combination of markers (inflammation, oxidative stress, endothelial activation [33, 34].

Notably, ED may be measured through the determination of surrogate end-organ effects. As an example, brachial FMD and EndoPAT measure peripheral vasodilator response. Ultrasound-measured carotid intima-media thickness (cIMT) is a structural measure of chronic endothelial damage and atherosclerosis. High pulse wave velocity (PWV) or augmentation index, reflecting arterial hardening, is a more highly advanced effect of long-term ED. Biomarkers together with functional tests (see below) provide a more comprehensive view of endothelial health. To recap it all, ED biomarkers are diverse ranging in terms of molecule (ADMA,

cytokines, endocan), cells (endothelial microparticles, progenitor cells), or functional vascular tests[35, 36].

ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION AND CARDIOVASCULAR INJURY OR DISEASE

Atherosclerosis and Ischemic Heart Disease

Endothelial dysfunction is generally accepted as one of the key initial events in atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. As a matter of fact, the loss of the endothelium-derived NO and antithrombotic properties leads to lipid infiltration and plaque formation [7, 37, 38]. With damaged endothelium, the positively charged lipoproteins (LDL) have an easier time penetrating the intima, oxidize, and induce inflammatory response. The adhesion molecules lead monocytes to the vessel wall where they transform into macrophages and foam cells which emit cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6) which further damage endothelium and invite additional immune cells [5]. Another occurrence in chronic inflammation is that the endothelium may experience endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EndMT), which leads to the instability of fibrous cap [39]. With the further development of the plaques, the endothelium continues to become dysfunctional at the top, which exposes the pro-thrombotic components (tissue factor, vWF) to the plaque rupture. Therefore, ED is the basis of the stable development of plaques as well as the acute events (MI, stroke) that result of the erosion or rupture of the plaque [40] According to the recent review by Li et al. Endothelial dysfunction is a central contributor to the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, which contributes to the plaque formation, inflammation, and thrombosis. They not only identify the classical factors (lipids, shear, NO deficiency) but also discover the novel information: the heterogeneity of endothelial cells through single cell

transcriptomics; the aggravation of injury by gut-derived metabolites (TMAO, homocysteine); the amplification of vascular inflammation by [40]exosomes.

ED is clinically identifiable many years prior to the appearance of angiographic lesions. Asthmatic measures of FMD at the periphery and RH-PAT are predictors of increased carotid intima-media thickness and coronary calcification. ED also foreshadows atherosclerotic disease: such as low FMD of healthy individuals foreshadows future MI and stroke. Therefore, ED is an atherogenesis marker and mediator [10, 41]. In acute coronary syndromes, ED is aggravated: damaged myocardium and systemic inflammation (e.g. IL-6, catecholamines) lead to an explosion of ROS which temporarily impairs endothelial activity. Recent experiments with patient-derived endothelial cells revealed that in the aftermath of ST-elevation MI, coronary endothelial cells are characterized by cell-autonomous metabolic reprogramming - increased ROS production, switching to pentose-phosphate and glutaminolysis to form glutathione - as a basis of their dysfunction [42]. Such findings underscore the intimate link between acute ischemia and endothelial pathology.

Hypertension

Endothelial dysfunction and hypertension have a complex, bidirectional relationship[24]. Basically, hypertension is a major cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality worldwide, and it is intimately associated with endothelial dysfunction, an early modification of the arterial endothelium that occurs before cardiovascular events. In healthy capillaries, endothelial cells and vascular smooth muscle cells regulate blood pressure by producing vasodilators like nitric oxide (NO) in response to blood flow, thereby maintaining a balance between endothelium-derived relaxing

factors (EDRFs) and contraction factors (EDCFs)[43]. Endothelial dysfunction upsets this equilibrium, lowering NO-mediated vasodilation while boosting inflammatory activation, which promotes vasoconstriction. This generates a vicious cycle in which endothelial dysfunction contributes to hypertension, and high blood pressure worsens endothelial function [44]. Therefore, Chronic hypertension imposes mechanical forces on endothelium resulting in micro-injury and facilitating the development of a pro-inflammatory, pro-thrombotic endothelial phenotype. On the other hand, ED also leads to hypertension by decreasing NO (important vasodilator) and raising vasoconstrictors (endothelin-1, angiotensin II). Mechanically, endothelial NO impairment results in an elevation of smooth muscle tone together with a decrease in vessel compliance. Oxidative stress and inflammation are also increased by endothelial dysfunction and make the arteries stiff and preserve high pressure [5].

Papa et al. (2022) summarize this interaction: the endothelial dysfunction-systemic arterial hypertension interaction may operate at multiple levels: the dysfunctional endothelial cells facilitate the increased reactivity of the vascular smooth muscle tone; secondly, the prothrombotic and proinflammatory systemic effects of the endothelial cell dysfunction enhance the action of systemic arterial hypertension thus resulting into the end organ damage damages. Therefore, ED is a cause, as well as a consequence of hypertension. In addition, ED severity is associated with the complications of hypertension (LV hypertrophy, nephropathy, retinopathy). The treatment of blood pressure can partially repair endothelial health but the best results of vascular can be achieved by addressing ED as well [9].

Heart Failure

Endothelial dysfunction is commonly observed in heart failure (HF), whether with reduced (HFrEF) or preserved (HFpEF) ejection fraction. In HFrEF, increased oxidative stress and reduced nitric oxide (NO) production impair endothelial function, while in HFpEF, low cardiac output and vascular congestion alter shear stress on the vessels. Additionally, pro-inflammatory conditions often driven by comorbidities like obesity and diabetes directly damage the endothelium and microvasculature in HFpEF. In both forms of HF, this widespread microvascular endothelial dysfunction leads to tissue hypoperfusion, pulmonary hypertension, and skeletal muscle impairment[45].

Rodella et al. (2024) highlight a two-way relationship between heart failure (HF) and endothelial dysfunction (ED): in HFrEF, neurohormonal activation and altered shear stress can impair endothelial function, increase reactive oxygen species (ROS), and reduce nitric oxide (NO) production, while in HFpEF, systemic inflammation contributes to endothelial damage[3]. ED in HF carries important prognostic significance, as impaired peripheral vasodilation is associated with poorer functional status and higher mortality. Interventions that enhance NO availability, such as exercise or pharmacological approaches, have been shown to improve exercise capacity in HF patients. Additionally, standard HF therapies including ACE inhibitors, ARNIs, beta-blockers, and SGLT2 inhibitors often provide added benefits by improving endothelial function. Current research is exploring strategies to promote endothelial repair, such as the use of endothelial progenitor cells, as potential adjunctive treatments in HF [45].

Myocardial Infarction and Acute Cardiac Injury

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is a key element in myocardial ischemia and infarction. In acute stage of myocardial infarction (MI), ischemia-reperfusion injury produces reactive oxygen species (ROS) and inflammatory mediators that exert further effect on the endothelial functioning of coronary and systemic vessels, thus leading to paradoxical vasoconstriction and no-reflow on the microvascular level. Pre-existing ED is also a risk factor of MI as it enhances the rupture and thrombosis of plaque. Post-MI ED can be persistent and contributes to undesirable cardiac remodeling with decreased nitric oxide (NO) inhibiting endothelium to prevent fibrosis and hypertrophy, causing maladaptive scar tissue. Post MI systemic ED is also associated with an increased risk of recurring events and heart failure. Recent reports, such as those of single-cell studies of human MI patients indicate that coronary endothelial cells react to injury by increasing oxidative and glutathione pathways maladaptively. Other ED-involving cardiac injuries include myocarditis or cardiotoxic chemotherapy, but are less researched. Surgical operations such as cardiac surgery and cardiopulmonary bypass induce systemic inflammation, which temporarily harms the endothelium, which is a cause of post-surgery complications. In general, any cardiac or vascular injury impairs the integrity of endothelial cells and reduced endothelial reserve exacerbates the disease [42].

Molecular and Cellular Pathways Involved

The nitric oxide (NO) pathway is critical to endothelial functioning. eNOS synthesizes NO using L-arginine and O_2^- and requires such cofactors as tetrahydrobiopterin, NADPH, and Ca^{+2} +/calmodulin. This occurs by activating signaling pathways (e.g., Akt/PI3K) by laminar shear stress to phosphorylate

eNOS at Ser1177 and stimulate NO production. NO releases to the smooth muscle, activating the guanylate cyclase, raising cGMP and causing vasodilation. It also prevents platelet aggregation, leukocyte adhesion and smooth muscle proliferation[46].

NO signaling is disrupted in endothelial dysfunction (ED). eNOS expression may be decreased or uncoupled, resulting in the formation of superoxide rather than NO. When superoxide reacts with NO, it reacts with NO to produce peroxynitrite that increases oxidative stress. Significant sources of ROS have been found to be dysfunctional mitochondria, NADPH oxidase (Nox1-4), xanthine oxidase, and uncoupled iNOS that are commonly upregulated by hypertension, diabetes, or smoking. There is often an overburden of antioxidant defenses (SOD, catalase, glutathione peroxidase). Further restrictions to NO signaling is reduced soluble guanylate cyclase activity or enhanced degradation of cGMP [28]

Inflammation worsens ED. NF- κ B activation by TNF- α , IL-1 β , or oxidized LDL promotes adhesion molecule and cytokine expression, while Nrf2 antioxidant signaling is often impaired. The NLRP3 inflammasome responds to ROS, cholesterol crystals, or TMAO, activating caspase-1 and IL-1 β to drive endothelial inflammation[47].

Shear stress is sensed by mechanosensors such as PECAM-1, VE-cadherin, and integrins. Laminar flow triggers protective signaling (PI3K/Akt, KLF2) that upregulates eNOS, thrombomodulin, and antioxidant genes, whereas disturbed flow activates pro-inflammatory transcription factors (NF- κ B, AP-1), promoting atherosclerosis at arterial bifurcations.[14].

Other pathways, like endothelin-1 (ET-1) and angiotensin II, shift toward

vasoconstriction and fibrosis in ED. Normally suppressed by NO and shear stress, ET-1 increases in hypertension and heart failure, further reinforcing vasoconstriction, inflammation, and vascular remodeling[24].

In summary, ED is the result of molecular dysregulation: decreased NO, excess ROS, pro-inflammatory signaling, and pro-thrombotic shifts. These changes at the cellular level culminate in impaired endothelium-dependent vasodilation, increased permeability, leukocyte adhesion, and thrombosis – the hallmarks of the ED phenotype.

DIAGNOSTIC TECHNIQUES AND IMAGING FOR ENDOTHELIAL FUNCTION

The study of the vascular function in coronary arteries is best conducted by the invasive coronary angiography with intracoronary infusion of the endothelial agonist like acetylcholine [46]. When a healthy artery is presented with low doses of acetylcholine, the effect is a vasodilation of the artery with the help of NO, and an increase in blood flow but with endothelial dysfunction, the effect may be dull or paradoxical (causing vasoconstriction)[46]. Coronary flow reserve or microvascular resistant measurements of doppler tipped wires may be investigated during the infusion of acetylcholine or adenosine, which offers an evaluation of the microvascular endothelial functionality. These invasive procedures are highly accurate (they are direct tests of the coronary bed) yet are only performed in research or with patients who already have angiography, because of the potentials of catheterization and vasoactive agents [48, 49]

Noninvasive approaches are routinely utilized for studying and screening endothelium function. Ultrasound assessment of brachial artery flow-

mediated dilation (FMD) is a common approach. A blood pressure cuff is inflated on the arm above systolic pressure for roughly five minutes and then abruptly released, resulting in reactive hyperemia. The higher shear stress increases NO release, [48]resulting in vasodilation, and the percentage increase in arterial diameter from baseline (FMD%) is recorded. Higher FMD% indicates improved endothelial function, whilst values below 5% suggest dysfunction. FMD has a small connection with coronary endothelial function and can predict cardiovascular events, but it is operator-dependent and requires defined standards for accurate assessment [50, 51].

Peripheral Arterial Tonometry (PAT) is another noninvasive device. This is based on the measurement of pulse volume amplitude with fingertip pneumatic probes. In reactive hyperemia (analogous cuff occlusion) the ratio between the post-to-pre occlusion pulse amplitude (the RHI index) is an indicator of microvascular endothelial functionality[52, 53]. RH-PAT records a small arterial tone with a significant amount of operator insensitivity. Research demonstrates that RHI is correlated to coronary microvascular activity and is predictive of cardiovascular events but represents mixed NO-dependent and independent processes. FMD and PAT have a low correlation implying that each measures a different vascular bed (brachial conduit and digital micro vessels although the two can be used to complement each other[52].

Ultrasound measures of chronic endothelial injury and atherosclerosis are Carotid Intima-Media Thickness (cIMT). However, despite not being a functional test, elevated cIMT is a validated cardiovascular risk predictor. Meta-analyses demonstrate that every 0.1 mm increase in cIMT would increase the risk of MI by approximately 10%. Carotid

ultrasound is simple and reproducible, but relies upon scanner resolution and operator expertise[36, 54].

More sophisticated imaging methods provide information on endothelial wellbeing. Coronary and peripheral function could be measured using Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). As an example, non-contrast measurement of the changes in coronary cross-sectional area and flow may be conducted in the presence of an endothelial stressor (i.e., isometric handgrip exercise) when combining MRI with isometric handgrip exercise. Healthy subjects experience coronary dilation and vasoprovance during handgrip, but patients with CAD do not. MRI has the ability to determine wall thickness and flow reserve that are non-radiative. Vascular inflammation in the endothelium and vessel wall can be detected with Positron Emission Tomography (PET) using tracers, such as, e.g., 18F-FDG, before the development of anatomic lesions. Intravascular optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and Intravascular ultrasound (IVUS), applied intravascularly can visualize the microstructure of the plaque and neovessels and provide insights into endothelial integrity of plaques (but is invasive) [36, 55].

In summary, endothelial function is assessed by a combination of tests: *Functional tests* (FMD, PAT, coronary reactivity) directly test vasodilator response, while imaging studies (cIMT, MRI, PET, IVUS) detect structural or molecular changes associated with dysfunction. No single test is perfect; often a tailored combination is used in research or specialized clinical evaluations [41, 46]

THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES

Pharmacological Interventions

Statins (HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors): Statins are the first-choice

lipid-lowering agents, which also have pleiotropic endothelial effects. They increase the eNOS activity, and NO synthesis, and decrease oxidative stress and inflammation. Statins significantly enhance endothelial function (increased FMD) in patients with metabolic syndrome or CAD and this effect is independent of LDL lowering. They also reduce the levels of CRP and NADPH oxidase activity, and maintain the bioavailability of NO. As an illustration, in MI patients high-dose rosuvastatin forgave FMD and reactive hyperemia index [56, 57]. Table 1 summarizes statins and other major therapies.

ACE Inhibitors / ARBs: These antihypertensives also have positive impact on ED. They prevent vasoconstriction and oxidative stress by inhibiting angiotensin II (or increasing bradykinin). ARBs (losartan) decrease endothelin-1 and inflammatory cues and ACE inhibitors augment bradykinin (NO-stimulator) and limit AngII-induced ROS. ACE inhibitors/ARBs are better than other antihypertensives at improving FMD as demonstrated by meta-analyses. As an example, perindopril and ramipril have been found to enhance endothelial functioning among hypertensive and CAD patients [47, 58].

Calcium Channel Blockers: Dihydropyridine calcium blockers (e.g. amlodipine) result in vasodilation and minor antioxidant activity. They are able to enhance endothelium-dependent dilation by decreasing shear stress and stopping proliferation of the smooth muscles. Nonetheless, the impact on NO biology is not so direct, and the evidence is not so strong as ACEi/ARBs.

β -blockers: Traditional β -blockers like atenolol do not improve endothelial function and may even make it worse because they reduce heart rate, which

lowers shear stress on blood vessels. In contrast, newer β 1-selective blockers such as nebivolol and carvedilol have added vasodilatory properties. Nebivolol, for example, increases nitric oxide availability through β 3-receptor stimulation, while carvedilol has antioxidant effects. These actions help relax blood vessels and improve endothelial function, making them more beneficial for vascular health compared to older β -blockers [59, 60].

Nitrates and NO Donors: NO is directly donated by organic nitrates (nitroglycerin, isosorbide), which causes a relaxation of vasoconstriction. Although useful in acute angina, chronic administration causes tolerance, and produces less impact on baseline endothelial health[61].

Phosphodiesterase-5 Inhibitors: Such medications as sildenafil increase cGMP production by preventing its degradation. Some studies have demonstrated that they enhance peripheral and pulmonary endothelial functioning, particularly in the HFpEF or pulmonary hypertension environment. The Sildenafil RELAX trial of HFpEF was not endpoint met, but PDE5 inhibitors are of interest, especially to microvascular ED[62, 63].

Lipid-lowering agents beyond statins: PCSK9 inhibitors (evolocumab, alirocumab) not only further lower LDL, but also reduce vascular inflammation and oxidative stress, improving endothelial function after acute coronary syndromes. Other agents like niacin and fibrates have less direct evidence on endothelium, though they modify lipid subfractions that affect ED [64].

Antidiabetic agents: There are some endothelial advantages of some diabetes drugs. Metformin enhances the availability of NO, decreases insulin resistance, and oxidative stress. SGLT2 inhibitors (empagliflozin, dapagliflozin) and GLP-1

receptor agonists have also been found to increase NO and anti-inflammatory processes, enhancing FMD in diabetic and HF patients. The PPAR- α inhibiting thiazolidinedione series (e.g. pioglitazone) stimulates PPAR- α and has anti-inflammatory effects with a small effect on endothelial-dependent dilation [65].

Antioxidants and Cofactors: Since oxidative stress is the cause of ED, supplements such as vitamin C/E in large dosages or L-arginine have been considered, however, large trials have not produced any significant findings. Supplementation of tetrahydrobiopterin (BH₄) to recouple eNOS is more specific: small studies indicate that it may reestablish NO activity in some situations.

New antioxidants (mimetic SOD enzymes, NADPH oxidase inhibitors) are being examined.

Anti-inflammatory treatments: Due to the presence of inflammation, anti-inflammatory treatments such as colchicine (NLRP3 inflammasome), IL-1 (canakinumab) and IL-1 β receptor (adalimumab) have demonstrated vascular outcomes. Colchicine decreased cardiovascular events after MI and small subanalyses indicated that it might enhance endothelial markers in subpopulations of patients. The use of the NLRP3/IL-1 pathway is a promising approach to treating ED-induced atherosclerosis. The NLRP3/IL-1 β pathway is a promising strategy to ameliorate ED-driven atherosclerosis.

Table 1: Summary of major pharmacotherapies and their endothelial effects.

Therapy	Mechanisms on Endothelium	Examples
Statins	\uparrow eNOS/NO, \downarrow ROS and inflammation (\downarrow CRP), stabilize endothelium	Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin
ACE Inhibitors/ARBs	\downarrow AngII and \uparrow bradykinin \rightarrow \downarrow ROS, \downarrow endothelin; \uparrow NO bioavailability	Lisinopril, Losartan
Calcium Channel Blockers	Vasodilation, reduce shear stress; some \uparrow NO indirectly	Amlodipine
β-Blockers (vasodilating)	\uparrow NO (nebivolol) or block sympathetic ROS \uparrow	Nebivolol, Carvedilol
Nitrates/PDE5 inhibitors	Exogenous NO, \uparrow cGMP, vasodilation	Nitroglycerin, Sildenafil
PCSK9 Inhibitors	\downarrow LDL, \downarrow vascular inflammation, \downarrow oxidative stress	Evolocumab, Alirocumab
Antidiabetic drugs	\uparrow NO, \downarrow inflammation via metabolic effects	Metformin, Empagliflozin
Antioxidants (experimental)	Scavenge ROS, restore eNOS cofactor (BH ₄)	Tetrahydrobiopterin
Anti-inflammatory	Inhibit cytokines/NLRP3 to reduce endothelial inflammation	Colchicine, IL-1 inhibitors
Endothelin Receptor Antagonists	Block ET-1 vasoconstriction/inflammation	Bosentan

Lifestyle and Behavioral Interventions

Non-pharmacological interventions are central to maintaining and restoring endothelial health, forming the foundation for cardiovascular protection. Regular

physical activity is one of the most effective strategies, as aerobic and interval exercise increase shear stress on vessel walls, stimulates eNOS activity, enhances nitric oxide production, and strengthen

antioxidant defenses, resulting in improved vascular function. Dietary modification is equally important, with Mediterranean-style diets rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, omega-3 fatty acids, and polyphenols shown to reduce oxidative stress, improve lipid profiles, and promote NO bioavailability, while processed foods, excess salt, and trans fats worsen endothelial dysfunction. Weight reduction and strict metabolic control further support vascular health by lowering pro-inflammatory adipokines, improving insulin sensitivity, and reducing advanced glycation end-products, especially in diabetes. Additionally, lifestyle measures such as smoking cessation, stress management, moderation of alcohol, and adequate sleep provide further endothelial protection by reducing oxidative and inflammatory stress. Together, these interventions not only improve endothelial function but also complement pharmacological therapy, making them the cornerstone of long-term cardiovascular health[28].

In summary, lifestyle changes that reduce oxidative/inflammatory insults and promote physiological shear (via exercise) are powerful remedies for ED. These interventions often amplify pharmacological therapy and should be the foundation of any strategy to restore endothelial health.

Novel and Emerging Therapies

Beyond traditional drugs and lifestyle, cutting-edge therapies targeting endothelial repair are in development[66].

Endothelial Progenitor/Stem Cell Therapies: Endothelial progenitor cells (EPCs) and angiogenic cells of the bone marrow can home to injured endothelium and repair. In experimental studies, the delivery of EPCs to ischemic limbs or myocardium has been found to improve neovascularization and limb or myocardial

performance. Preliminary clinical trials (primarily in peripheral artery disease or refractory angina) indicate that autologous progenitor cell infusions have a small beneficial effect on microvascular perfusion, and potentially FMD. The methods of mobilizing endogenous EPCs (e.g. using cytokines such as GM-CSF) or bioengineering of stronger endothelial-colony-forming cells are under investigation. These methods are to salvage the damaged endothelium itself[52].

Gene Therapy: Gene transfer methods have been shown to treat endothelial signaling. As an example, the expression of the VEGF gene (through adenovirus or plasmid) into ischemic tissue enhances local angiogenesis and has been tested in refractory angina patients. Equally effective, an eNOS or endothelial-derived antioxidants (superoxide dismutase) gene therapy has been promising in preclinical models. It has been limited by vegetable safety issues of testing in clinical trials, although new vectors and CRISPR technologies are being evaluated. The concept is to directly activate protective (eNOS, antioxidant genes, anti-inflammatory cytokines) or inhibit harmful (ET-1, AngII receptor) endothelial genome pathways.

Nanomedicine and Drug Delivery: Nanoparticles are currently being designed to target dysfunctional endothelium with drugs. As a case in point, antioxidant nano-particles or siRNA targeting inflammatory factors can be delivered to inflamed vessels, eliminating the systemic side effects. Experimental but promising methods of locally rescuing endothelial functions include nanoparticle conjugates of nitric oxide donors or mTOR inhibitors (used as anti-senescence).

Exosome-based Therapies: Endothelial and stem cell-derived exosomes

(microvesicles filled with RNA, proteins) have the capacity to carry non-regulated repair signals. One of the strategies is the injection of engineered exosomes that can carry microRNAs or proteins that facilitate eNOS/ angiogenesis. Initial animal evidence has shown that exosomes of healthy endothelial cells may enhance endothelial injury.

Gene Editing/CRISPR: It could be possible to work on the precise editing of endothelial genes in the future. An example of this is fixing a genetic defect of low eNOS activity or inhibiting ET-1 receptors which would give potentially long-lasting endothelial repair.

These new therapies are more experimental therapies, although they represent a transition towards direct intervention of endothelial biology. Emerging technologies such as nanotechnology, stem cell therapy, and genetic therapy are highly promising in enhancing the endothelial functions and reversing atherosclerosis. The issues that are currently being faced are the method of delivery, safety, and showing long-term benefit. However, there is a high rate of development in regard to specifically designed therapies that focus on repairing a defective endothelium [67, 68].

RECENT ADVANCES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Research on endothelial dysfunction has gained new momentum over the last five years with new knowledge being discovered. Endothelial heterogeneity has been discovered in high-throughput omics studies: Single-cell RNA sequencing of human vessels has found specialized subtypes of endothelial cells with specific roles in inflammation and repair. Indicatively, some groups of endothelial cells in a partial endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EndMT) have been associated with the susceptibility of

plaques. Research in metabolomics has suggested new mediators like the gut microbiome-derived metabolite trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) and increased homocysteine as the cause of endothelial damage. These findings point to the interconnectedness of systemic metabolism and endothelial health[4, 32].

The other revolutionary thing is the identification of endothelial cell metabolism. The study by Zodda et al. (2024) in eLife showed that the human coronary endothelial cells of MI patients are altered to a highly coupled mitochondrial state, excessively producing ROS, and upregulating pentose-phosphate and glutaminolytic pathways to compensate. These autonomous metabolic variations indicate novel targets (e.g. PFKFB3, glutaminase) to avert post-MI endothelial malfunction [42]. These cell-autonomous metabolic changes suggest new targets (e.g. PFKFB3, glutaminase) to prevent post-MI endothelial dysfunction.

Candidates such as endocan and others have been developed as a result of biomarker research. Preclinical trials of novel imaging probes of early endothelial inflammation (e.g. VCAM-1-directed MRI agents) are underway. In future noninvasive endothelial phenotyping may be possible using artificial intelligence and machine learning in applied to imaging (such as retina or nailfold capillaroscopy). SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 agonists have been known to have endothelial effects in therapeutics other than glycemic control. Gene therapy is being investigated involving the role of microRNAs (e.g. miR-126, miR-92a) in endothelial repair. Endothelial progenitor cell therapy trials in diabetic vasculopathy, in reperfusion injured models are under recruitment. Endothelial grafts may become a possibility in the future with improvements in biomaterials and bioreactor grown endothelium [47]. Taken together, all these

changes are indicative of a future in which endothelial dysfunction is no longer handled in a symptomatic manner but at multiple levels: metabolic reprogramming, gene and cell therapy, immunomodulation, and precision imaging. A combination of traditional methods (reduction of the risk factors) and these new strategies is the future of the cardiovascular medicine[[67]].

CONCLUSIONS

Endothelial dysfunction is at the core of cardiovascular disease. A healthy endothelium actively prevents illness, whereas its dysfunction causes atherosclerosis, hypertension, myocardial damage, and heart failure. The hallmark characteristics of ED are decreased NO, increased oxidative stress, inflammation, and prothrombotic signaling which have been widely studied and several biomarkers as well as assays can detect their existence. In clinical practice, ED serves as an early warning symptom and prognostic marker for a variety of cardiovascular disorders. Fortunately, ED is at least somewhat reversible and established medicines (statins, ACE inhibitors, exercise, and nutrition) improve endothelial function, while emerging treatments (stem cells, gene therapy, innovative medications) show promise for restoring endothelial health. Ongoing research reveals deeper molecular pathways, bringing up new diagnostic and treatment options. For clinicians and researchers, endothelial dysfunction remains a critical target: understanding and treating it is key to preventing and mitigating cardiovascular injury.

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